

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CLINICAL AND DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PERSONALITY DISORDERS IN PERSONS WHO HAVE COMMITTED SOCIALLY DANGEROUS ACTS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the results of a study of the clinical and dynamic characteristics of personality disorders in persons who have committed socially dangerous acts; a clinical, dynamic and socio-psychological analysis of the factors that determine the aggressive criminal behavior of subjects with personality disorders is carried out.

Keywords: personality disorders, socially dangerous act, aggressive behavior.

Introduction. Socially dangerous actions of persons with mental disorders remain one of the important problems of general and forensic psychiatry. Two main aspects can be distinguished in this problem – the allocation of clinical criteria for forensic psychiatric assessments of mental disorders in defendants who have committed aggressive acts, and the recommendation to prescribe coercive medical measures. In the forensic psychiatric assessment of certain mental disorders and the justification of compulsory medical measures, it is necessary to take into account the psychopathological, psychological, motivational, situational and social factors that influence the socially dangerous behavior of the subject [3, 5]. Forensic psychiatric examination of persons with mental disorders who have committed unlawful acts also requires taking into account such important parameters as “aggression” and “aggressiveness”, their connection with the current mental state.

The problem of aggression, in general, has long been studied in the following aspects: the definition of the concepts of “aggression”, “aggressiveness”, the systematics of individual forms of aggressive behavior. The most important and topical issue is the assessment of the conditionality of aggression by mental pathology. This fully applies to the study of aggression in subjects with personality disorders. A direct link between aggressive criminal acts and personality disorders was pointed out by many authors [4, 6, 8].

Of particular importance to the problem of aggressive behavior of subjects with personality pathology is given in a forensic psychiatric clinic, where this disorder occurs quite often. During the forensic psychiatric examination of subjects with personality pathology accused of committing aggressive criminal acts, in addition to studying the structure, depth and dynamics of personality disorder, great importance is attached to the motivation of illegal actions, the influence of social factors. The study of the criminal behavior of subjects with personality disorders also shows the high importance of the psychological component of the analysis of the behavior of subjects during the period related to the acts they are charged with [7, 9, 10]. This is especially important in the forensic psychiatric assessment of mental disorders that limit the ability to realize the actual nature and social danger of their actions or to control

them. An urgent problem also seems to be the determination of the degree of public danger required when recommending coercive medical measures, which are part of the prevention of repeated aggressive criminal acts.

Thus, the forensic psychiatric significance of personality disorders in the examination of the accused is realized in three main aspects: - clinical and diagnostic (determining the depth of personality disorders, ascertaining dynamic shifts); criminological (mainly when assessing a personality disorder as a prerequisite for committing certain illegal acts); expert (forensic psychiatric assessment of personality disorders and recommendation for the appointment of compulsory medical measures).

In recent years, criteria for forensic psychiatric assessments of personality disorders have been intensively developed [1, 2]. At the same time, it should be pointed out that generalized studies of socially dangerous acts committed by persons with various types of personality disorders were not carried out, a forensic psychiatric assessment of personality disorders was not developed, issues of determining social danger were not developed, which is necessary, in particular, when recommending outpatient forced observation and treatment by a psychiatrist. The foregoing determines the relevance of this study.

The purpose of the study is to study the clinical and dynamic characteristics of personality disorders in persons who have committed socially dangerous acts.

Material and research methods. The study examined 58 men with personality disorders who committed socially dangerous acts. The main research methods were clinical-psychopathological and statistical, as well as experimental-psychological, sexological, paraclinical. Statistical processing included an assessment of the frequency of the analyzed features – absolute value, percentage share, as well as the reliability of the studied features (p index) and their relationship (correlation – R index).

Research results. In typological terms, the study group was represented mainly by persons with emotionally unstable personality disorder (30 people – 51.7%), hysterical personality disorder (17 people – 29.3%) and 11 (19.0%) – mixed personality disorders (Fig 1).

Fig.1. The contingent of examined patients

Analysis of socio-demographic data showed that the majority of the study group had a low level of education. Many could not adapt to the conditions of military service and labor activity. Their family adaptation was disturbed, intra-family relations were conflicting. At the same time. They adapted quite well in specific subcultures, in particular, criminal ones. This position is confirmed by criminological data. The surveyed had earlier and more frequent prosecutions. The study of the features of the formation of personality pathology showed that 33 (56.9%) individuals had a history of hereditary burden with a predominance of alcoholism and drug addiction (21 people – 36.2%) over other mental pathology.

An analysis of the characteristics of the upbringing of the surveyed showed that the surveyed were significantly more often brought up in conditions of hypocustody, neglect, rejection by their parents, were subjected to physical punishment, humiliation. Relationships with peers in childhood and adolescence can be characterized as equal, partnership, or they occupied a leading position.

Psychopathologically aggravated heredity, pathology of the early period of development, unfavorable social conditions of upbringing and development contributed to the appearance of frequent pathocharacterological reactions in childhood and puberty. During such periods, the subjects showed aggressive behavior, they left school, wandered, and used psychoactive substances. Further aggravation of pathocharacterological reactions formed personality disorders.

In 18 surveyed (31.0%), aggressive and auto-aggressive forms of reaction took place since childhood, which manifested themselves in increased irritability, pugnacity, loudness, cruelty to animals, self-harm, which may be due to a low level of socialization and approval of aggressive forms of behavior. Microenvironment.

The surveyed noted increased sensitivity to external influences, psychological stress and internal biological changes in the body that occurred throughout life. These factors changed the clinical picture of personality disorders. There was a temporary sharpening of character traits, or there were long-term reactions and personality development. Such changes in the state of psychopathic personalities are known as the dynamics of personality disorders, which are characterized by states of compensation and decompensation. Among decompensations, there are acutely emerging states of sharpening of personality traits – characterological (psychopathic) reactions – and a relatively long-term personality development (paranoid development). The states of decompensation were the reason for the primary diagnosis in the examined personality disorders.

Dynamic shifts in the examined persons arose in objectively and subjectively significant psychotraumatic situations in the form of characterological reactions. Such reactions were characterized by an increase in the main pathological manifestations of personality pathology, the appearance of anxiety and affective tension within the limits of the personality's resources. Usually psychopathic reactions were short-term, lasting from several hours to several days. In the development of dynamic shifts, changes in the clinical picture of personality disorders and in the implementation of aggressive urges, the use of psychoactive substances was important. It should be noted the high number of people who abuse psychoactive substances (22 people – alcohol, 15 people – other psychoactive substances).

Negative dynamic shifts disrupted the socialization of the subjects and contributed to the development of aggressive criminal behavior. The aggressive crimes committed by the subjects of the first group were predominantly of a property nature. They more often than others committed robberies, robberies, accompanied by threats, physical violence, often killing the victim

(31.0%). In such situations, their actions were especially cruel. Criminal actions were preceded by the use of alcoholic beverages or drugs, which facilitated the onset of aggression. They often committed planned crimes in a group of people, acting as a leader.

Conclusion. Thus, aggressive illegal behavior is characteristic of persons, mainly with emotionally unstable, hysterical and mixed personality disorders (excitable, hypersthenic types). Aggression as a personality trait is formed in childhood and adolescence against the background of adverse factors (mainly microsocial and psychological) and exacerbates the dynamics of personality disorder. Clinical-dynamic and socio-psychological analysis revealed factors that determine the aggressive criminal behavior of subjects with personality disorders: improper upbringing and unfavorable psychotraumatic environment in a family with child abuse; substance abuse; repeated criminal acts in history; acute and chronic traumatic situations preceding the aggressive delict, negative dynamic shifts.

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METHOD OF DIRECT PROSTHETICS IN PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS

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ABSTRACT

Indices of hygiene, gingival bleeding and RMA are significantly better in patients with proposed direct prosthetics in the long term after prosthetics compared with the period before treatment and in the group of patients in whom direct prosthetics were not used. Conclusions. the design of a direct fixed aesthetic prosthesis has advantages over other methods of orthopedic treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis of the II degree of development.

Keywords: generalized periodontitis, direct prosthetics, bone tissue atrophy, hygiene indices, bleeding gums.